
Perceptions, Knowledge, and Practices regarding Childhood Convulsions among Reproductive Age Women in Orlu L.G.A., Imo State, Nigeria

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Abstract: Childhood convulsions, characterized by involuntary disturbances of brain function, are common in pediatric populations, particularly in developing regions where misconceptions and traditional practices prevail. This study explores the perceptions, knowledge, and preventive or therapeutic practices related to childhood convulsions among women attending antenatal and immunization programs in a rural primary healthcare center in Orlu Local Government Area, Imo State, Nigeria. A cross-sectional descriptive study was conducted involving 130 women, using a semi-structured, interviewer-administered questionnaire. Data analysis included frequency distributions and statistical tests to identify significant associations between variables. Most respondents (90%) had prior knowledge of childhood convulsions, with fever identified as the most common perceived cause (38%). Despite high literacy levels, misconceptions regarding treatment and prevention persisted, with palm kernel oil (19%) being the most frequently reported intervention during convulsions. While 92% believed convulsions were preventable, only 33.5% sought medical attention for febrile conditions. Although awareness of childhood convulsions was relatively high, significant gaps in knowledge and reliance on traditional practices underscore the need for targeted health education campaigns to improve evidence-based management and prevent complications associated with convulsions in children.

Keywords: Childhood, convulsion, perception, knowledge, practices.

1. Introduction

Convulsion, which is characterized by an abrupt, involuntary contraction of muscles and often associated with loss of consciousness, may be due to several conditions and diseases [Sottosanti, 1998]. One of the common causes is high fever especially in young children. Convulsion can also be due to infections such as meningitis or metabolic derangements such as hypoglycemia among others. Although convulsions and seizures are interconnected, they do not exactly mean the same thing. Seizures enclose a wider gamut of symptoms which may occur in the absence of convulsion; while convulsion on the other hand is a distinct type of seizure that is associated with uncontrolled muscle contractions [Citizens Speciality Hospital, 2025].

Febrile Convulsion

Febrile convulsion constitutes the most frequent type of convulsion in children aged 6 months to 6 years [Srinivasan *et al.*, 2005]. It occurs in 2%-5% of children [Millar, 2006; Rosman, 2003; Shah *et al.*, 2002; Vestergaard *et al.*, 2004] and involves certain outcomes such as parents' panic as well as increased risk of seizures in general [Azubike & Nkanginieme, 2007; Gordon *et al.*, 2000]. Although the main pathology of febrile convulsion remains to be

known, genetic factors have been incriminated in the process, as in 60%-70%, a history of convulsion exists in one of the parents or siblings. Fever with convulsion remains an important and one of the commonest emergencies among children in the tropics. The commonest cause (in the tropics) is malaria. Others are upper respiratory tract infections, pneumonia, urinary tract infections, viral infection and otitis media [Parmar *et al.*, 2001].

Although the occurrence of febrile seizures in childhood is quite common, they can be extremely frightening, emotionally traumatic and anxiety provoking when witnessed by parents. During the seizure, the parent may perceive that their child is dying [Deng *et al.*, 1996; Varity, 1998], but fortunately most febrile seizures are benign. Rarely have febrile convulsions caused by brain damage [Gordon *et al.*, 2001] and except for developing countries, there are no documented cases of febrile seizure-related deaths on record [Varma, 2002]. There have been numerous reviews and updates which have explored the natural history, treatment and subsequent outcomes of febrile seizure [ILAE, 1993].

Febrile seizures have been defined by international League Against Epilepsy (ILAE) as “a seizure occurring in childhood after one month of age, associated with a febrile illness not caused by an infection of the central nervous system, without previous neonatal seizure or a previous unprovoked seizure, and not meeting the criteria for other acute symptomatic seizure [Bethune *et al.*, 1993]. The occurrence of a child’s first (initial) febrile seizures has been associated with first or second degree relative with a history of febrile and afebrile seizure [Haslam, 2000].

The abrupt onset of the abnormal motor activities and the accompanying impairment or loss of consciousness is a dreadful and frightening experience to parents who may desperately employ all manners of available therapies in an effort to abort the convulsions [Angyo *et al.*, 1997; Fagbule *et al.*, 1991; Iloeje, 1989; Izuora & Azubike, 1997; Osuntokun, 1969], while convulsion would have resolved spontaneously with minimal morbidity and mortality as obtained in technically advanced countries [Okoji *et al.*, 1993]. Various emergency home therapies employed in developing countries bring about poor outcome [Angyo *et al.*, 1997; Fagbule *et al.*, 1991; Iloeje, 1989; Izuora & Azubike, 1997; Osuntokun, 1969]. From the study conducted by Ofove *et al.* [2002] to determine the knowledge, attitude, and practices of home management of febrile convulsions among rural and urban mothers in two Edo villages of south southern Nigeria, it can be noted that the sociocultural beliefs about illnesses are precursors to treatment seeking behavior.

Social Implication of Convulsion

Seizure in childhood may interfere with family life, sleep and social life of parents, imposing tremendous stress and anxiety on them. It may also cause irreparable damage to the child. Providing sufficient information to the parents about the relationship between fever and seizure as well as the benign nature of the disease is an important measure for relieving their stress and anxiety [Ling, 2000; Shojaezadeh, 2000]. A study by Ling suggested that most mothers lack a proper understanding of the disease and its prevention [Ling, 2000]. Children with seizure disorder face social discrimination and stigma due to negative perception, lack of knowledge, and understanding of the condition [Billinghurst *et al.*, 1973; Osuntokun & Odeku, 1970]. This social discrimination against persons suffering from epilepsy often may be due to sudden falls and convulsive episodes at unexpected times in public places resulting in rejection [Saegpattrachai *et al.*, 2010]. Sometimes, the social discrimination against these persons may be more devastating than the disease itself. Children with epilepsy may be rejected from their classes because of frequent seizures which makes their teachers and fellow students uncomfortable with their presence in class [Ndour *et al.*, 2004]. Also, some others are not enrolled in schools once the school authority becomes aware of that such a child has epilepsy [Prpic *et al.*, 2003]. Other social aspects of life are also adversely affected by the disease [Sell Salazar, 2009]. Older children and adults with epilepsy usually have problems with adaptation, institutionalization, and access to public accommodation [El Sharkawy *et al.*, 2006]. The disease may also cause unemployment and difficulty to marry when the children get to adulthood. Affected persons may be rejected from social events because there are people that still believe that the disease may be transmissible by contact with the patient’s saliva. The attitudes toward people with epilepsy are influenced by the degree of knowledge of the condition [El Sharkawy *et al.*, 2006; Parmar *et al.*, 2001; Sell Salazar, 2009]. Many parents still have a negative attitude about epilepsy. Some of them feel it is contagious and as such during an attack, some are not assisted in anyway [Saegpattrachai *et al.*, 2010; Wu *et al.*, 2008]. The availability of antiepileptic drugs and the prolonged medical care needed by children

with epilepsy justify the careful planning of a social program for this public health problem. More so, studies have shown that parents and siblings of children with seizure disorder are more prone to psychiatric and emotional problems than parents and siblings without seizure [Aronu & Iloeje, 2011; Aronu & Ojinnaka, 2009]. The academic performance of children with seizure disorder who still go to school despite stigmatization has been shown to be lower than that of children without the seizure disorder [Ibekwe *et al.*, 2007; Trimble, 1986]. Though many factors are reported to be responsible for the poor academic performance, stigmatization and discrimination have been documented as the most devastating [Wright, 1975]. As school children with seizure disorder spend most of their daytime socializing and interacting with their teachers as well as their schoolmates, these teachers therefore play an important role in public health education. They can hand on knowledge to their pupils and extension to the community. Several studies on the public knowledge of seizure disorder in Asia reported a positive attitude to seizure disorder among the educated people compared to the uneducated [Pan & Lim, 2000; Ramasundrum *et al.*, 2000]. Knowledge and attitude to seizure disorder is also reported to be influenced by the socio-cultural environment in which the individual is resident [Iivanainen *et al.*, 1980].

Rationale for the study

Convulsions disrupt brain function, leading to social stigma for affected children. Despite improved awareness, local remedies persist as common management strategies.

Objectives

1. To determine the knowledge of childhood convulsion among reproductive age women in Orlu L.G.A.
2. To know the women's practice of treatment of fever and prevention of childhood convulsion.
3. To determine the commonest age group (s) that presents with childhood convulsion.
4. To know the social implications of childhood convulsion among reproductive age women in Orlu.
5. To determine the women's perception of the commonest cause (s) of convulsion.

2. Methods

Study design:

This is a cross-sectional descriptive study carried out in Orlu Nigeria to understand the perception of childhood convulsion among reproductive age women in Orlu.

Hypotheses for the Study:

Null Hypotheses (H₀):

1. There is no significant relationship between women's educational level and their knowledge of childhood convulsion causes and management.
2. There is no significant association between the age of respondents and their perception of the common causes of childhood convulsion.
3. There is no significant difference in the methods of treating childhood convulsion among women with different socioeconomic backgrounds.

Alternate Hypotheses (H₁):

1. Women's educational level significantly influences their knowledge of childhood convulsion causes and management.
2. The perception of childhood convulsion causes significantly varies with the age of respondents.
3. Methods of treating childhood convulsion differ significantly among women with varying socioeconomic statuses.

Study Setting and Target Population

This study was conducted among reproductive age women attending immunization and antenatal care (ANC) program in Orlu Health Center, Orlu Local Government Area (LGA) Imo State Nigeria. The study was conducted in Orlu Health Center (located adjacent to Chesire Home in Amaifeke Orlu LGA) because of its strategic location and as the Primary Health Center serves all the communities in Orlu LGA. Hence, it can be said to be a good representation of study population. Although there are other PHCs in Orlu LGA, most of them are non-functional,

do not run ANC and immunization programs and their locations are not central. Therefore, those PHCs majorly serve the communities in which they are located and thus not a good representation of the study population.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion criteria for this study involved women of reproductive age (between 18 and 51 years) who are resident within Orlu LGA.

Women who were not within the reproductive age range and those not resident within Orlu LGA were excluded from the study. Those who have completed the study in a previous ANC or immunization visit were also excluded from the study.

Research Approach and Sampling Technique

Quantitative research approach was used to determine outcome variables such as knowledge, preventive practices, and social implications of childhood convulsion using age, education, occupation and religion as predictors in a 31-item semi-structured questionnaire.

Study Timeline and Sample Size

This study was conducted in the months of January and February 2014. As at the time of the study, the Primary Health Center used for the study ran their immunization program on Mondays and Thursdays and their antenatal care on Tuesdays and Fridays. About 20 to 30 children are attended at each immunization day and about 7-10 women are seen in each antenatal visit.

The minimum sample size for the study was determined using the formula for descriptive estimating a single population proportion:

$$N = Z^2 PQ$$

where n= required sample size; Z = Z-score for 95% confidence interval (1.96)

D2 P = estimated proportion of positive perception (0.5 is used since there was no know prevalence); Q = 1 – P = 0.5; D = the desired margin of error which was estimated to be ±8.8% at 95% confidence interval.

Substituting for the above, a sample size of 125 was obtained. The sample size was rounded up to 150; however, 130 participants completed all the sections of the study.

Statistical Methods

Data manually and electronically analyzed using frequency tables, SPSS, and excel sheet. Significance tests applied where necessary (p<0.05).

Ethical Consideration

Ethical approval was obtained from the College of Health Sciences, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Nnewi Campus Nigeria at the time of the study. Participants provided informed consent, and confidentiality was assured throughout the study.

Bias

Efforts to address bias through clear explanation of study objectives to participants and by using culturally appropriate administration procedures.

3. Results

Participants

A total of 130 women of reproductive age completed the study.

Demographics: Majority (93.8%) were married, with a mean age of 28.5 ± 8.8 years. Education levels were predominantly tertiary (47.7%) or senior secondary (44.6%). Occupations: Traders (46.9%) and civil servants (29.2%).

Descriptive Data:

Knowledge:

- 90% had heard of childhood convulsions. Fever was the most common cause identified (38%).
- Most participants (64.6%) were aware of prevention methods, and 92.2% believed convulsion is preventable.

Practices:

- Palm kernel oil was the most common local remedy (19%). Few used orthodox treatments like paracetamol

Outcome Data

O Social Implications: 64.6% were comfortable associating with children with convulsions, while 30.8% advised seeking hospital care.

Main Results

O Harmful practices like forcing substances into the mouth or making incisions on the child persist despite awareness. Fever management often relied on local remedies.

Statistical Associations

Educational attainment was positively correlated with awareness of proper preventive measures ($p < 0.05$). However, misconceptions and reliance on traditional remedies were observed across all educational groups.

Table 1: Social demographic characteristics of the respondents.

Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age Range (Years)		
20 and below	7	5.4
21-25	42	32.3
26-30	46	35.4
31-35	19	14.6
36-40	6	4.6
41-45	5	3.9
46-50	3	2.3
Greater than 50	2	1.5
Total	130	100.0
Marital Status		
Single	5	3.8
Married	122	93.8
Divorced	3	2.4
Widow	0	0.0
Others, please specify	0	0.0
Total	130	100.0
Respondents' highest level of education		
No formal education	0	0.0
Primary	5	3.8
Junior Secondary	5	3.8
Senior Secondary	58	44.6
Tertiary	62	47.7
Others	0	0.0
Total	130	100.0
Respondents' occupation		
Student	18	13.9
Civil Servant	38	29.2
Farmer	0	0.0
Trader	61	46.9
Housewife	10	7.7
Others (catering, NYSC, etc)	3	2.3
Total	130	100.0

Knowledge about Childhood Convulsion

The results of knowledge about childhood convulsion are presented in Tables 2-11.

Table 2: Ever heard about childhood convulsion.

Have you heard about childhood convulsion before?	Frequency	Percentage (%)
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Yes	117	90.0
No	13	10.0
Total	130	100.0

Table 3: Know any child who has had convulsion before.

Do you know of any children who have had convulsion before?	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	117	90.0
No	13	10.0
Total	130	100.0

Table 4: Age of the child with convulsion.

How old was the child? (years)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Less than 1	37	25.5
1-5	74	51.1
6-10	17	11.7
11-15	7	4.8
16-20	3	2.1
More than 20	7	4.8
Total	145	100.0

Table 5: Causes of convulsion.

What do think causes convulsion?	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Inherited from parents	16	7.8
Malaria	59	28.8
Immunization	8	3.9
Other feverish conditions	78	38.0
Head injury	9	4.4
Brain infections	7	3.4
Evil spirit/demonic attack	25	12.2
Others (not immunizing the child, transfusing the child blood form an infected person)	3	1.5
Total	205	100.0

Table 6: Whether convulsion is infectious.

Do you think convulsion is infectious?	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	28	21.5
No	102	78.5
Total	130	100.0

Table 7: How others may become infected with convulsion.

If yes, how do you think others can be infected?	Frequency	Percentage (%)
By touching the person	3	5.8
By sleeping with the person	3	5.8
By eating with the person	5	9.6
By sharing the same cloth or other materials with the person	3	5.8
By sitting with/near the person	3	5.8
By touching the foams/saliva from the person's mouth during convulsion	14	26.9
By transfusing the person's blood to another person	21	40.4
Others, please specify	0	0.0
Total	52	100.0

Table 8: Knowledge of the complications of convulsion.

Do you know of any complications of convulsion?	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	85	65.4
No	45	34.6
Total	130	100.0

Table 9: Possible complications of convulsion.

If yes, what are they?	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Developmental delay	43	23.5
Poor academic performance	32	17.5
Mental retardation	43	23.5
Death	60	32.8
Disability	1	0.6
Disfiguration	1	0.6
Make the child dull	1	0.6
Loss of consciousness	1	0.6
Brain injury	1	0.6
Total	183	100.0

Table 10: Free association with a child with convulsion.

Do you think it is good to associate freely with or allow your child/ward to associate freely with a child that have convulsion?	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	84	64.6
No	46	35.4
Total	130	100.0

Table 11: Advice to a parent whose child has convulsion.

What advice can you give to a parent that has a child with convulsion?	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Abandon the child	0	0.0
Take the child to a special school	8	3.8
Treat the child very well	78	37.0
Allow the child to interact with or associate with others	19	9.0
Take the child to the hospital when he/she is convulsing	65	30.8
Take the child to a herbalist/native doctor	16	7.6
Take the child to a prayer house	25	11.8
Others, please specify	0	0.0
Total	211	100.0

Treatment/Prevention of Convulsion

The results of treatment/prevention of convulsion are presented in Tables 12-19.

Table 12: Talk on the prevention of convulsion.

Have you had a talk on prevention of convulsion?	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	84	64.6
No	46	35.4
Total	130	100.0

Table 13: Knowledge on whether convulsion is curable or preventable.

Do you think convulsion can be cured or prevented?	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	120	92.3
No	10	7.7
Total	130	100.0

Table 14: What people do when a child is convulsing.

What do you do or see others do when a child is convulsing?	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Rub the child with olive oil	22	5.5
Rub the child with palm kernel oil	76	19.0
Force olive oil into the child's mouth	24	6.0
Force palm kernel oil into the child's mouth	70	17.5
Force cow's urine into the child's mouth	5	1.3
Force the parents/sibling's urine into the child's mouth	32	8.0
Make some marks on the child's body	16	4.0
Put your hands or spoon or any other object into the child's mouth	34	8.5
Position the child to a safe place	15	3.8
Warm/heat the child's limbs	13	3.3
Give the child some herbal concoctions	15	3.8
Give the child orthodox drugs	4	1.0
Take the child to a herbalist	9	2.3
Take the child to a prayer house	16	4.0
Take the child to the hospital	36	9.0
Leave the child for the convulsion to stop by itself	2	0.5
Bathe the child with cold water	4	1.0
Expose the child	1	0.2
Give the child crude oil	1	0.2
Give the child onion	3	0.8
Give the child ogwuude(herbal ointment)	1	0.2
Rub palm kernel oil in the child's eye/anus	1	0.2
Total	400	100.0

Table 15: Result of the treatment given.

Was there any positive result from the treatment given above?	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	83	63.9
No	32	24.6
Don't know	15	11.5
Total	130	100.0

Table 16: Treatment of fever.

How do you treat your child when he/she develops fever?	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Bathe him/her with warm water (tepid sponge)	32	11.6
Bathe him/her with cold water	70	25.5
Give him/her paracetamol	62	22.5
Take the child to a chemist	12	4.4
Take the child to the hospital	92	33.5
Others (put off the child's cloth, etc.)	7	2.5
Total	275	100.0

Table 17: Knowledge of any orthodox drugs used to treat or prevent convulsion.

Do you know of any orthodox drugs used to treat or prevent convulsion?	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	37	28.5
No	93	71.5
Total	130	100.0

Table 18: Knowledge of local/herbal agents used to treat/prevent convulsion.

Do you know of any local/herbal agents used to treat/prevent convulsion?	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	45	34.6
No	85	65.4
Total	130	100.0

Table 19: Source of information about the agents used in treatment/prevention of convulsion.

How did you know about these drugs/agents?	Frequency	Percentage (%)
From a doctor	28	25.2
From a nurse	7	6.3
From a chemist	9	8.1
From a herbalist	4	3.6
From a friend/neighbor	42	37.8
From the media (radio, television, newspaper, etc.)	5	4.5
From community meetings	3	2.7
From the church	2	1.8
From the market	4	3.6
Others, (parents, family members, etc.)	7	6.3
Total	111	100.0

4. Discussion

Key Results

This study highlights that although knowledge of childhood convulsions among the participants was high (90%), significant gaps remain in terms of appropriate prevention and treatment practices. Traditional remedies such as the use of palm kernel oil and harmful practices like forcing substances into the mouth were prevalent, while reliance on orthodox medical interventions was low.

Comparison with Other Studies

The findings of this study align with and provide further insights into existing research in Nigeria and other developing countries:

- i. **Knowledge of Convulsion Causes:** The perception of fever as a leading cause of convulsion (38%) aligns with findings from studies conducted in Ilorin, Port Harcourt, and Ondo Nigeria, where febrile seizures were also commonly recognized as a primary concern among mothers (Ofovwe *et al.*, 2002; Anigilaje & Anigilaje, 2012; Abiodun & Ayinbomwan, 2025). However, this study's finding of a notable minority attributing convulsions to supernatural causes (e.g., demonic attacks, 12.2%) underscores the persistent influence of cultural beliefs, which was less prominent in urban studies.
- ii. **Traditional Remedies:** The reliance on palm kernel oil as a treatment measure mirrors findings in Port Harcourt where 64.3% of respondents used palm kernel oil for convulsions (Ofovwe *et al.*, 2002). In contrast, studies in Ilorin highlighted cow urine concoctions as the predominant remedy (Lorngurum & Okwaji, 2010), studies in Kaduna, Ilesa, Ondo, Benin City, and Port Harcourt, noted cold bath (Eseigbe *et al.*, 2014; Olubosede *et al.*, 2021), mother's urine (Abiodun & Ayinbomwan, 2025), scarifications (Nwaneri & Okunola, 2019) or doing nothing (West & Onubuogu, 2019) suggesting regional variations in traditional practices.
- iii. **Orthodox Medical Practices:** Only 33.5% of participants in this study preferred taking febrile children to the hospital, reflecting similar trends in Sokoto and Ibadan, Nigeria, where 32% and 89.4% relied on hospitals for managing febrile convulsions or childhood convulsion (Zaini *et al.*, 2013; Abaribe *et al.*, 2023). This highlights a shared challenge in access to or trust in formal healthcare services across diverse Nigerian communities.
- iv. **Social Implications:** This study found that 64.6% of respondents were comfortable associating with children who have convulsions, a higher proportion compared to the studies in Enugu and Bayelsa, where stigma was more pronounced (Frank-Briggs & Alikor, 2011; Jack-Ide *et al.*, 2015). This suggests that social stigma may be less entrenched in some areas potentially due to tighter community bonds and shared experiences while it not be the same in other locations.

Limitations

This study faced several limitations:

1. **Sampling Size and Bias:** The sample size was small, and the study conducted in a single health facility, which might limit the generalizability of findings to other settings. Also, conducting a household study may yield a more generalizable result as it may likely capture reproductive age women who for several reasons such as

personal, religious, etc. neither attend ANC during pregnancy nor immunize their children. This could also account for the educational status of participants, as women who are educated are more likely to attend maternal and child health care.

- 2. Reluctance to Participate:** Some respondents were hesitant to answer questions, potentially introducing response bias. Some respondents also did not complete all the questions, and their removal reduced the sample size for the study.
- 3. Financial Constraints:** Resource limitations may have restricted the scope and depth of the study.

Interpretation

The persistence of traditional remedies and harmful practices highlights the need for targeted health education campaigns. While formal education has improved awareness, it has not significantly translated into safer management practices. The observed reliance on local remedies is likely influenced by cultural beliefs, ease of access, and affordability.

In comparison to studies conducted in more urbanized settings, such as Enugu and Lagos, this study reveals that rural communities might have fewer resources and less exposure to evidence-based health practices. However, there is also a lower degree of stigma in associating with children who have convulsions, as 64.6% of respondents were comfortable interacting with such children. This is higher than the results from urban studies, suggesting that social stigma may be less entrenched in rural areas.

Generalizability

These findings are relevant to a developing country such as Nigerian and similar low-resource settings where traditional beliefs and practices intersect with limited healthcare access. Future interventions should account for cultural contexts and emphasize the importance of evidence-based management.

Recommendations

- 1. Community Health Campaigns:** Leverage local gatherings like village meetings, churches, and market days to promote awareness of safe convulsion prevention and treatment practices.
- 2. Healthcare Integration:** Train local healthcare providers to serve as trusted sources of information to counteract harmful traditional practices.
- 3. Research:** Conduct further studies to evaluate the efficacy and safety of commonly used local remedies, like palm kernel oil, to provide evidence-based guidance.

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